

Information sheet 2.07

Delimitation of buffer zones

This information sheet is a supporting document to Appendix A ('Standardised checklist of risk reduction options') of the Guidance of the EFSA Plant Health Panel on quantitative pest risk assessment.

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A. Description of the RRO

ISPM 5 defines a buffer zone as "an area surrounding or adjacent to an area officially delimited for phytosanitary purposes in order to minimize the probability of spread of the target pest into or out of the delimited area, and subject to phytosanitary or other control measures, if appropriate" (ISPM 5). The objectives for delimiting a buffer zone can be to prevent spread from the outbreak area (Figure 1A) and to maintain a pest free production place (PFPP), site (PFPS) or area (PFA) (Figure 1B).

Figure 1: Goals of a buffer zone. 1A to prevent pest spread. 1B to maintain a pest free production place or site. Green area = Buffer zone; red area= area where the pest of concern is present; blue area=protected area.

A buffer zone is targeted at natural spread of the pest. As the pest of concern may be present at low prevalence in the buffer zone, RROs targeted to detect and either contain or eliminate the pest must be in place ensuring the conditions of PFA, PFPP or PFPS and the isolation of outbreak. This can be achieved by directly acting on the pest and/or its potential vectors and/or their host plants and the size of the buffer zone, which is directly dependent on the rate of natural spread of the pest (complex).

Both ISPM 10 (Requirements for the establishment of PFPP and PFPS) and ISPM 22 (Requirements for the establishment of areas of low pest prevalence) provide some recommendations on the requirements related to buffer zones. In particular ISPM 10 indicates that the extent of the buffer zone should be determined on the basis of the distance over which the pest is likely to spread naturally during the course of the growing season. Monitoring surveys should be conducted at adequate frequency over one or more growing seasons. The action to be taken, if the pest is detected in the buffer zone, will depend

on the requirements of the NPPO. The pest free status of the place of production or production site may be withdrawn or appropriate control measures may be required in the buffer zone. In any case, access for surveys or control measures should be verified in advance. If appropriate, adequate procedures may be established to support the assurance that pest freedom is maintained (local reporting/notification and publicity, local regulation, control/elimination of detected pests).

B. Risk factors

To maintain pest free buffer zone there are two prerequisites. First, a reliable and timely surveillance system (e.g., able to detect latent infections or early infestation stages) should be in place to detect all new outbreaks in the buffer zone. Second, reliable and timely eradication measures should be available to keep the buffer zone pest free in case of detection.

C. Parameters to consider regarding the effectiveness of the RRO

The feasibility and effectiveness of a buffer zone in protecting a PFA, a PFPP, a PFPS or in isolating an outbreak is dependent on:

(a) The biology of the pest concerned:

- The host plant range determines the feasibility of host plant removal as a possible control measure in the buffer zone. Furthermore, the host plant range of the pest determines the number of individual plants under surveillance in the buffer zone.
- The dispersal mode and rate determines the minimum size of the buffer zone to prevent introduction in the area or place of concern. For instance, in the case of the invasive western corn rootworm (*Diabrotica virgifera virgifera*) Carrasco et al. (2010) assessed the effectiveness of the minimum widths for the buffer zone using a spatial individual-based model of the dispersal for one generation of adults. Adult dispersal and mortality were estimated to assess the effectiveness of the buffer zone.

(b) The heterogeneity of the environment:

- Size of buffer zone (100m, 1km, ...)
- Host plant density and distribution in buffer zone: For species with a narrow host range (e.g. no wild host plants) removal of all host plants in a buffer zone may be a feasible option or compulsory crop rotation could be envisaged.
- Population pressure of pest in surrounding areas.
- Habitat fragmentation. Several theoretical studies indicate that spread rates are affected by habitat fragmentation. For example, Ewers and Didham (2006) analysed the species responses to habitat fragmentation and indicated how confounding factors either masked their detection, or prevented their manifestation. In that context geographical barriers (irregularities) may limit dispersal of a pest.

The probability distribution of the effectiveness of the buffer zone can be estimated based on the size of the buffer zone and the probability distribution of escapees as indicated in figure 2.

Figure 2: Relation between buffer zone size and dispersal capacity of the organism under scrutiny with the effectiveness of the measure.

(c) the effectiveness of the control measures applied in the buffer zone depends on:

- Official control to prevent human-assisted introduction
- Reliable surveillance system (detectability, ...)
- Reliable eradication of new outbreaks
- Removal of host plants (including crop rotation).

Depending on the context, the factors under consideration are different.

- E.g.1 In the context of prevention of infestation by harmful organisms hosted by weeds in Ukraine, Ustinova and Munko 2013 suggest to consider the following factors when establishing the buffer zones:
 - dispersal distance of the harmful organism during a growing season,
 - presence of host-plants of the harmful organism,
 - presence of natural barriers limiting dispersal of the organism.
- E.g.2 APPPC RSPM 2005 suggests to consider the following factors when delimiting a buffer zone for preventing re-infestation by fruit flies of a PFA:
 - pest suppression techniques which may be used to reduce the fruit fly population including: selective insecticide bait spraying, sterile insect technique, male annihilation technique, biological control, mechanical control;
 - the target fruit fly species and its biology, host availability, cropping systems, natural vegetation including adjacent forest or natural ecosystems, climatic conditions;
 - the geographic features of the area under consideration; and the proximity of large urban areas that may make the control of fruit fly species of economic concern difficult and/or costly.

D. Applicability / feasibility of the RRO

Different limitations are linked to the feasibility of this measure:

- technical limitations: the delimitation of the buffer zone should take into consideration the natural (active and passive) dispersal capacity of the pest (e.g. flight distance) and human assisted passive spread in the area (e.g. roads, railways) and should allow surveillance and intervention in the area;
- regulatory limitations: if protected species are growing in the delimited area and would be affected by associated control measures;
- economic and social limitations: the potential host plants grown in the buffer zone might be subjected to stringent measures.

Depending on the measures to be applied against the pest (if they are very specific/costly, etc.), it may not be feasible to implement them if the buffer zone is very large.

E. Other RROs that may lead to similar effect

Not applicable.

F. Combinations of RROs that include this RRO

The buffer zone is intended to remain pest free. Therefore is always combined with:

- pest monitoring surveys,
- pest identification, e.g. visual inspection,
- control measures to eliminate the pest or its vectors, e.g. pesticides,
- control measures to eliminate host plants, e.g. roguing.

The buffer zone is usually delimited before the implementation of pest control measures as the area should be perimetral to either the infested area (Fig 1A) or the PFA, PFPP, or PFPS (Fig 1B).

When a buffer zone is a measure included in PFA, PFPP or PFPS strategy, it is often an integrative part of eradication and containment programmes.

G. Conclusion

Synoptic table for the RRO

RRO	Target	Area of application	Expected effect	Main technical limitations of use	RROs with similar effects / most often in combinations
Buffer zone	All pests (and their vectors) and Host plants	Perimeter of an outbreak area or Perimeter of a production area/site	Prevent spread of the pest to uninfested areas. Ensure a place of production remains pest free.	Nature and size of the area to delimit based on the pest biology (e.g., flight distance)	Measures for achieving pest eradication or containment, PFA and PFPP.

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